

Action of Bases on Complex Compounds derived from Organic Thio-compounds and Platinic Chloride.

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In continuation of the work on the action of organic thio-compounds upon chloroplatinic acid, the behaviour of methyl sulphide towards chloroplatinic acid has been studied and the following compounds have been isolated :—

(i) $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$; (ii) $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$; (iii) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$.

These compounds have been subjected to the action of bases like ethylamine, pyridine, etc., and a study of the resulting products has been found to throw considerable light on the constitution of the parent bodies (*cf.* Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 155; Rây, Bose-Rây and Adhikary, *ibid.*, 1927, 3, 476; Rây, Bose-Rây and Rây-Chowdhury, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 139).

The products are mostly well-known compounds of the Werner type, some of which have already been obtained by previous workers by the action of bases on similar complex compounds of platinum (Rây and collaborators, *loc. cit.*). This suggests that the compounds (i), (ii) and (iii) possess the Werner constitution.

Constitution of $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, etc.

The compounds $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ may be represented as normal compounds of quadri- and bi-valent platinum respectively.

That the compound (i) is practically a non-electrolyte has been shown by conductivity measurement in acetone solution, thus supporting the constitution given.

The compound (ii) $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, when boiled vigorously with water, breaks up into $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.

Action of Bases on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.

By the action of ethylamine, piperidine and pyridine respectively upon $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, the following compounds have been obtained:—

(iv) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{EtNH}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; (v) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (vi) $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$

In the compounds (iv) and (v) the platinum is bivalent while in (vi) it is tetravalent. So it is evident that in some cases the compound $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ is reduced and at the same time the Me_2S radicles are replaced by the bases, but in the other, the valency of platinum is not altered, the base simply replacing the sulphide radicles. The constitution of the compounds may be represented as follows:—

The complete ionisability of the chlorine atoms in (iv) was proved directly. No ionising solvent for the compound (v) however could be found, so that its constitution could not be proved directly. The compound (vi) is well-known and can have no other constitution than that suggested above.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Methyl Sulphide upon Platinic Chloride.

An excess of methyl sulphide was added to an aqueous solution of platinic chloride at the ordinary temperature. The whole was then cooled in ice-water as the heat evolution during the reaction was very great. As the reaction proceeded, orange yellow mealy crystals began to settle down. After an hour, when the reaction was complete, the crystalline product was filtered from the mother-liquor

and washed successively with water, alcohol and acetone. The purified compound was then dried in a vacuum. (Found: Pt, 45.74; Cl, 24.55; S, 14.82. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt, 45.82; Cl, 25.03; S, 15.07 per cent.).

The mother-liquor, on evaporation, gave an impure product which was perhaps a mixture of different compounds.

Preparation of the Compounds $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.

The compound $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ was boiled with water for a long time and filtered hot in the pump. A part of the compound went into solution. The process was repeated several times until the soluble constituent had been completely removed. The insoluble residue was dried. It dissolved in boiling acetone from which it separated out as bright yellow crystals. (Found: Pt, 42.20; Cl, 30.51; C, 9.78; H, 2.67; S, present. $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt, 42.29; Cl, 30.80; C, 10.41; H, 2.61; S, 13.9 per cent.).

The aqueous extract was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid and a pale yellow crystalline compound was obtained. This was twice recrystallised from water. (Found: Pt, 49.80; Cl, 17.66, S, present. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt, 50.00; Cl, 18.20; S, 16.4 per cent.).

This compound has also been obtained by a different method (Blomstrand, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, *ii*, 38, 359; Klusom, *ibid.*, 1903, *ii*, 67, 24).

Conductivity Measurement of $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ in acetone solution.

Weight of the substance taken = 0.6657 gm. Cell constant = 0.1535.

Dilution.	Observed resistance.	Calculated molecular conductivity.
69260 c.c.	13600 ohms.	0.6688
138520	23200	2.17

The very low molecular conductivity shows that the compound is not ionised in the solvent, thus agreeing with the constitution of the substance suggested previously.

Action of Bases on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.

(a) *Ethylamine.* On mixing $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ and an excess of aqueous ethylamine (30%) great heat was evolved and the platinum compound gradually went into solution. On concentration of the solution white crystals began to separate out. These were filtered off, washed with a little water and recrystallised from it. The compound

melts with decomposition at 211°. (Found: Pt, 40.20; Cl, 14.85; N, 11.85. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{EtNH}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pt, 40.48; Cl, 14.73; N, 11.62 per cent.). Sulphur was found to be absent.

(b) *Piperidine*. $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ and an excess of piperidine were thoroughly mixed, when much heat was evolved. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for fifteen minutes to complete the reaction. The bright yellow colour of the compound changed to yellowish white. The insoluble mass was then filtered, washed with a little piperidine and then digested with water to remove piperidine hydrochloride formed during the reaction. The residue was then washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried in a vacuum. (Found: Pt, 41.28; Cl, 15.64; N, 5.80; S, absent. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pt, 41.31; Cl, 15.04; N, 5.93 per cent.).

(c) *Pyridine*. $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ and an excess of pyridine were thoroughly mixed. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 15 minutes and then filtered, washed with a little pyridine and then with water to remove pyridine hydrochloride formed during the reaction. The residue was then washed with alcohol and ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The compound forms yellow crystals. (Found: Pt, 39.08; Cl, 28.27; N, 5.48; S, absent. $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Pt, 39.39; Cl, 28.6; N, 5.65 per cent.).

This compound had previously been obtained by Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 160) by a different method.

Action of Bases on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.

The action of the four bases, *e.g.*, aniline, benzylamine, ammonia and pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ has already been described (Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *loc. cit.*, pp. 157, 361). In the former paper the authors showed that the bases ammonia and pyridine on interaction with $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ simply replace the two sulphide radicles and in the latter paper the authors have shown that the tetravalent platinum is first reduced to the bivalent condition by the action of aniline and benzylamine and then the two sulphide radicles are replaced by two or four molecules of the base.

In the present work it has been shown that, after the reduction of platinum from the tetravalent to the bivalent stage, the replacement of the two sulphide radicles takes place step by step, and intermediate compounds are sometimes obtainable. In some cases when the base is very reactive, the replacement of the two sulphide

radicles takes place so rapidly that no intermediate compound could be isolated. But in the case of some other bases, *e.g.*, diethylamine, trimethylamine, etc., the reaction may be arrested at the intermediate stage.

The following scheme illustrating the principle suggested:—

The formation of compounds of the type (vii), (ix), (x) and (xi) has already been noticed (*loc. cit.*). A compound of the type (viii) and that intermediate between (vii) and (viii) have been isolated during the present investigation, *e.g.*,

- (xii) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{NH}$ (Type viii)
 (xiii) $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{NH}$ (Type intermediate between vii and viii)
 (xiv) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{Me}_3\text{N}$. (Type viii)

Action of Bases on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.

(a) *Diethylamine.* $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ was treated with an excess of diethylamine (30% aqueous soln.) and the whole was allowed to stand overnight. This was then filtered and washed with water to remove completely the hydrochloride of the base formed during the reaction. It was then further washed with alcohol and ether and dried in a vacuum over sulphuric acid. The compound was pale yellow and insoluble. (Found: Pt, 45.05; Cl, 16.95; S, 7.19; N, 3.16. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{NH}$ requires Pt, 45.45; Cl, 16.55; S, 7.46; N, 3.26 per cent.).

simultaneous reduction. The compound may be represented by (xvi)

(xvi)

Action of Bases upon $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}$.

(a) *Propylamine.* $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}$ was treated with an excess of anhydrous propylamine at 0° and the mixture was kept overnight in a closed vessel. The mass became viscous. On the addition of water the brown colour of the mass disappeared and a white precipitate separated out. This was filtered and washed with water and alcohol. The product was crystallised from hot water when colourless needles, m.p. 198° with decomposition, were obtained. (Found: Pt, 36.57; Cl, 13.47; C, 26.39; H, 7.44. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pt, 36.24; Cl, 13.19; C, 26.76; H, 7.74 per cent.) Sulphur was found to be absent.

(b) *Diethylamine.* A mixture of $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}$ and an excess of diethylamine was kept for two days in an air-tight flask. An insoluble yellow compound gradually settled down. This was filtered, washed with water and then with alcohol. The yellow mass was then crystallised from benzene, filtered, washed with alcohol and ether. (Found: Pt, 35.93; Cl, 13.85; S, 5.13; N, 2.61. $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{NH}$ requires Pt, 35.20; Cl, 12.82; S, 5.79; N, 2.53 per cent.).

(c) *Diethylamine.* An excess of methylamine (alcoholic solution) was treated with $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot (\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}$ at 6° and kept overnight in a closed vessel when the substance went into solution from which a light greenish crystalline compound separated out. This was filtered and washed repeatedly with boiling benzene to remove any unchanged $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}$. The residue was then washed with alcohol and then with water to remove the hydrochloride of the base formed during the reaction. The purified compound was finally washed with alcohol and ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. (Found: Pt, 65.75; Cl, 23.14; N, 4.78. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{MeNH}_2$ requires Pt, 65.65; Cl, 23.90; N, 4.71 per cent.).

